

**IMPROVING THE ACCOUNTING OF THE EXPENDITURE OF EXTRA-
BUDGETARY FUNDS IN INSTITUTIONS OF THE PUBLIC EDUCATION
SYSTEM.**

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Abstract: This article describes the correct organization of areas for spending extra-budgetary funds in institutions of the people's education system, as well as their accounting. Accounting information was used to study the problems associated with the expenditure of funds in institutions of the people's education system and to form analytical information on expenditures on extra-budgetary funds. This, in turn, necessitates the research of methodological foundations related to the accounting and expenditure of extra-budgetary funds in institutions of the people's education system, as well as the development of proposals for their solution, identifying existing problematic situations.

Key words: extra-budgetary savings, income, actual expenses, cash costs, funds, analytical information.

As we know, in institutions of the people's education system, it is important to correctly organize the areas of expenditure of extra-budgetary funds, as well as to maintain their accounting, study the problems associated with the expenditure of funds, and form analytical information on expenses for extra-budgetary funds. This, in turn, necessitates the research of methodological foundations related to the accounting and expenditure of extra-budgetary funds in institutions of the people's education system, as well as the development of proposals for their solution, identifying existing problematic situations.

Today, the most important issue in our country is the reduction of budget financing in budget organizations, the creation of additional sources of financing through the formation of extra-budgetary funds. Extra-budgetary funds are used to finance certain expenses, that is, these are funds that are created at the expense of other sources, and not funds from the state budget. At the moment, there are 10,764 institutions of the public education system in our country, with the aim of financing them in 2022, 30,823.4 billion from the state budget, the sum was diverted and from this we can see that the total secondary education costs increased by 1.18 times compared to 2021.

Based on the requirements of the present day, the improvement of the realization of products (work, services) specific to the type of activity in the institutions of the people's education system, the application of measures taken to the practice of the use of income and expenses and other funds are among the

necessary issues. Based on the spheres and directions of activity of institutions of the people's educational system, extra-budgetary funds are formed.

The formation of extra-budgetary funds is carried out according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 3, 1999 No. 414 "on improving the procedure for providing funds to budget organizations." In accordance with this decision, the liquidation of accounts payable of extra-budgetary funds is spent on strengthening the material base, social protection and material incentives for employees of a maximum of 25 budgetary organizations.

According to the regulation "On the procedure for the formation and use of funds of extra-budgetary funds of organizations in the Public education system" and "On the procedure for the provision of paid educational services in general secondary educational institutions in the system of the Ministry of Public education " which were signed in institutions of the public education system No. 243, 343, the proceeds of extra-budgetary funds are formed and expenses are made at their expense.

Today, it is important to study and improve the existing problems of the formation of extra-budgetary funds in budgetary organizations, the procedures for the use of these funds for the purposes established by law, the correct maintenance and control of their accounting, etc.

The movement to attract extra-budgetary funds in the institutions of the people's education system should not undermine its main activity, the mission of the institution, it should be remembered that the institution of the people's education system is not a commercial organization, therefore it is necessary to develop marketing issues in it based on the needs and needs of society, and

Only if we freely and independently dispose of the extra-budgetary funds formed in the institutions of the people's education system, we can see the growth of extra-budgetary funds. In accordance with the Regulation No. 243 "on the procedure for the formation and use of funds of extra-budgetary funds of institutions and organizations in the people's education system", it is necessary to implement the following proposals to improve the accounting of spending in institutions of the people's education system consideration of legislation on budget and extra-budgetary funds, amendments and additions to documents adopted a long time ago, to the requirements of the time, development of regulatory legal acts corresponding to international experience clarification of the benefits and costs provided to budgetary organizations increasing the interest rate of social protection and material incentives or paying 25% of the

amount spent not from the proceeds problems arising from the consumption of funds in institutions where extra-budgetary funds are formed, having the right to freely direct the funds

In conclusion, it can be noted that only if we freely and independently dispose of the extra-budgetary funds formed in the institutions of the people's education system, we can see an increase in extra-budgetary funds.

References:

- 1."Fuqoralar uchun byudjet." 2022yil loyiha. Toshkent 2021 yil.
- 2.O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 1999 yil 3 sentyabrdagi 414-sonli "Byudjet tashkilotlarini mablag' bilan ta'minlash tartibini takomillashtirish to'g'risida"gi Qarori.
- 3.243-son bilan ro'yhatdan o'tgan "Xalq ta'limi tizimidagi tashkilotlarning byudjetdan tashqari jamg'armalari mablag'larini shakllantirish va foydalanish tartibi to'g'risida"gi nizam. 2021 yil 27 aprel.
4. 343-son " O'zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta'limi Vazirligi tizimidagi umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida pullik ta'lim xizmatlarni ko'rsatish tartibi to'g'risida"gi nizam 2019 yil 22 aprel.
- 5.Bakaybayeva A.S. O'zbekiston Respublikasida budget hisobi va moliyaviy nazoratni takomillashtirish yo'llari. iqt. fan. fal. dok. dis. avtoreferati. –T.: 2020. – 52 b.; Ibragimov K.SH. Budget tashkilotlarida buxgalteriya hisobi va moliyaviy hisobotni takomillashtirish (Oliy ta'lim muassasalari misolida). iqt. fan. fal. dok. dis. avtoreferati. –T.: 2018. – 54 b.; Mehmonov S.U. Budget tashkilotlarida buxgalteriya hisobi: nazariya va amaliyot. Monografiya. – T.: "Iqtisod moliya"., 2016.;
- 6.Azamat Ostonokulov. Improvement of methodology for accounting of extra-budgetary resources of public educational and medical institutions. Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI). Volume 12, Issue 7, July 2021: 4857- 4867. SCOPUS.
- 5.Xudayberdiyev V. Byudjet tashkilotlarida byudjetdan tashqari tushumlarning shakllanishi va ishlatilish tartibi. Iqtisod va moliya 2015yil №12
- 6.Qarshiboyev O.S. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining rivojlantirish jamg'armasi xarajatlar hisobi.Iqtisod va moliya jurnali 2011yil №11
7. Абдыкадырова Э. У. М. Рахимова, И. Арабаева, Финансовый учет специальных средств в бюджетных учреждениях 25.11.17 Принята к публикации.